

ARBITRATION AND ITS EFFECTIVENESS IN CIVIL LITIGATION, A BRIEF STUDY OF BALOCHISTAN

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ARTICLE INFO:

Received: 28/10/2025

Accepted: 25/11/2025

Published: 27/11/2025

Keywords:

Arbitration,
Alternative Dispute
Resolution (ADR),
Jirga System, Conflict
Resolution,
Balochistan Informal
Justice, Legal
Practitioners'
Perspectives, Judicial
Views, Public
Awareness, Speedy
Justice, Legal Reform,
Pakistan.

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DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17766565>

ABSTRACT

In today's world arbitration is known n for its importance for resolving disputes, because arbitration is known for its flexible nature. Like other countries Pakistan has also adopted arbitration as a mode to resolve conflicts. In Baluchistan arbitration is known by the name "Jirga". So, this research will cover the effectiveness of arbitration in Balochistan. Basically, this research has qualitative methodology in which the viewpoints of Judges and legal practitioners are also involved so according to their viewpoint's arbitration is an informal method of conflict resolution. So, for establishment of efficient arbitration in Balochistan there must be public awareness. By adopting advancement in arbitration there will be improvement in saving time of the court. There will be less legal complexity and there will be speedy justice as ADR is the modern way for conflict resolution.

INTRODUCTION

Arbitration is known mostly by its method which means any litigation outside the court. As arbitration is a way or mode in which conflicts are solved. In the time saving less costly and conflicts are resolved in private manner, arbitration is a method that involves less complexity if we compare it with courts. Modern countries have also adopted arbitration when they are involved in only investment. Commercial or any trade activity. When Pakistan becomes signatory of the New York convention 1958 Pakistan has made this promise that it will domestically and internationally support arbitration. But despite of promise there was no practical implementation especially in Balochistan. In Balochistan there is still informal and tribal way of adjudication.

In Balochistan the Jirga System is the primary mode of resolving disputes and the legal system and social system of Balochistan are involved by tribal tradition. So, the Jirga System basically does not follow ethical legal and procedural standard which are mentioned in national and international laws for arbitration. There is poor enforcement of arbitration act 1940 in Pakistan like registration of arbitral award, its recognition and its enforcement is practiced but in limited domain. So, after watching this situation the litigants go for traditional system Jirga or went to court despite of knowing that it is time consuming practice.

The aim of the study is to critically analyse the arbitration effectiveness in Balochistan because arbitration is facing challenges in the cultural and legal sense. So, this study aims to improve the landscape of arbitration and propose its solutions. So, the focus of research is specifically on a region where arbitration is still underdeveloped. So, this research highlights the challenges that are faced by Pakistan for promotion of arbitration as arbitration is a modern tool for conflict resolution.

Background

If we look into the background of arbitration in early times when conflicts were resolved by means of customs, elders of community and different community's members which were known as local councils. In Balochistan this concept takes place by the name of Jirga in which disputes are resolved within community by the tribe's elder. The belief of people was that Jirga is the only way to resolve their issues as it was culturally adopted method of conflict resolution but Jirga system has very weak legal framework in terms of its enforcement.

The formal beginning of arbitration begins from south Asia through Indian Arbitration Act 1899 by British government but this Act was limited only to some major cities. That most marked twist and adoption came in 1940 when Arbitration Act of 1940. Still relying on traditional system rather than adopting arbitration.

The Research Problem

In Pakistan the civil litigation is mostly represented its complex procedure, very time consuming, long delays and expensive. Whereas arbitration flexible method it is affordable method and speedy justice is seen in arbitration.

The focus of research problem is that despite arbitration is flexible mechanism it is less costly it provides a cooperative environment there is party's autonomy, the proceedings in arbitration is

private but still in Balochistan the conflicts related to property family and business etc. remains unresolved because people don't adopt arbitration.

Significance Of the Research

This study highlights key problems and solutions that how the arbitration can be reformed.

- Firstly, it tells us about that arbitration can be practiced in Balochistan in effective manner.
- Secondly it highlights that arbitration plays important role in modern era providing access to justice.
- Thirdly the decisions made in arbitration can be helpful for legal practitioners and policy makes also.
- Finally, this study also shows that there can be reforms in legislation by adopting arbitration Act 1940 and weakness in Balochistan regarding Arbitration Act 1940.

Objectives of the Study

- The primary objective of the research is to demonstrate arbitration in civil litigation environment of Balochistan and how arbitration can be enforced and what are challenges of arbitration within Balochistan.
- The study further analyses the cultural and social barriers which are creating obstacles in arbitration effectiveness in Balochistan.
- Additionally, this research enables recommendations that to promote the resolution of disputes which are resolved through traditional manners can also be solved through the following of formal arbitration that meets with modern legal norms as well as local customs.

Research Questions

This research is followed by these questions:

1. Why there is lack of faith and confidence in litigations for adopting arbitration as a medium of conflict resolution?
2. How formal arbitration differs from Baluchistan's traditional customs?
3. Until which extent the arbitration proceedings can reduce judicial intervention by keeping in view the arbitration Act 1940?
4. For improving access to justice is it necessary to adopt formal arbitration in the province?
5. What are the challenges for Balochistan to practice effective arbitration?

Limitations of the Study

This research is limited geographically to the province of Balochistan. The primary data consists of interviews conducted with judges, lawyers, and professionals with expertise in dispute resolution, restricted by accessibility and availability. The analysis also relies on secondary data, which may be limited due to the scarcity of academic literature focusing specifically on arbitration in Balochistan. Despite these limitations, the study offers valuable insights into arbitration as practiced in a culturally distinct region. (Balochistan).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Basically, the method used in this research is “Doctrinal methodology” in support with qualitative data. In doctrinal research use understand the concept through judicial decisions, examine laws and case studies to understand the legal framework of arbitration. The secondary method used in this research is through international magazines, articles and books. The primary data was collected from ten legal practitioners, lawyers and judges in Balochistan. The interview analyses show problems faced by both litigation and practitioner in arbitration proceedings which are challenging while practicing arbitration. The data was analysed through thematic analysis and responses were also taken into categories like reforms, cultural barriers and weakness of institutions. So, the reliability of finding is strengthened by using mixed method approach.

DISCUSSION AND FINDINGS

So, it is disclosed and revealed through findings that Balochistan is facing lots of challenges in arbitration.

- Firstly, the Jirga System takes place because people believes that gives quick decisions and provides justice. However, they don’t know it does not cover their procedural rights and fundamental rights are also violated due to biasness.
- Secondly, the lack of trained arbitrators and specialized courts in Balochistan. The ambiguities in procedures, in arbitral awards there is slow procedure of enforcement which demotivates the litigants for speedy justice and its shows Arbitration Act 1940 does not meets with standards of modern arbitration.
- Thirdly, there is no awareness about arbitration which is a major barrier in Balochistan and people still believes that only courts is the only sole legitimate state-based mechanism.
- Fourthly The fundamental flaw is that in Balochistan there are no institutes of arbitration. So, to practice arbitration domestically and internationally there must be training programme, arbitration institutions and arbitration centres to fulfil the structural gap in a Balochistan.
- Fifthly, the ineffectiveness in arbitration is due to mistrust of public to the judicial system because judicial system requires judicial enforcement and litigant have fear and they perceived it as costly and slow process.
- Finally, People in Balochistan rely on cultural norms and those thinks that only this is the way to resolve disputes and there is no any other alternate for disputes resolution because they are unaware about arbitration.

So, these findings give indication that there is need of reforms to educational, cultural and institutional dimensions.

CONCLUSION

So, in a nutshell arbitration remains ineffective due to its cultural, legal and structural challenges as arbitration has the potential to improve civil dispute resolution in Balochistan. The reason that the Jirga is considered as dominant forum is due to lack of institutional support, the legislation is outdated and there is lack of public awareness. While Pakistan has taken steps internationally to modernize its arbitration frame work, but these reforms has not reached Balochistan. A successful reform that are required for arbitration are the reforms that are not only legally sound but socially acceptable reforms also. The major factors due to which arbitration is still underutilized is lack of public education, lack of public education, lack of institutional development and lack of legal modernization. So, these findings shows that there is need of strategy to bring reforms comprehensively that will lead to align with local customs as well as modern dispute resolution.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. **Encouragement in Commercial Arbitration:** Arbitration clauses must be adopted by trade association, investors and by business chamber.
2. **Judicial enforcement and support:** court should enforce arbitral award in an efficient manner and adopt on approach to arbitration.
3. **Public Awareness campaigns:** There is need to build trust on people and educating citizens about procedures and benefits regarding arbitration.
4. **Integration of tribal customs with statutory law:** Hybrid models can help to identify the major difference between local traditions and formal arbitration.
5. **To train arbitration, judges and lawyers:** for expertise in arbitration there is need of professional training programmes and seminars.
6. **Establishment of arbitration centres in Balochistan:** For providing accessible and affordable conflict resolution services there is need of district and regional level arbitration institutions.
7. **Key forms in the Arbitration Act of 1940:** To align this act with international standards there is need of procedures to be clarified and the Act need modernization to limit judicial intervention.

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